

Complex Compounds of Iridium. Part II.

Compounds of Organic Sulphides and Pyridine.

BY PRAFULLA CHANDRA RAY, NADIABEHARI ADHIKARI AND
RANAJIT GHOSH.

In a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 251) it has been stated that during reaction with organic sulphides, iridium tetrachloride first loses chlorine and that this reaction becomes accelerated in presence of alcohol. We have since then tried the same reaction in other media, *e.g.*, acetone, chloroform and benzene. In acetone, the reaction yields the same compound $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ even in cold along with a tarry residue. No appreciable reaction, however, takes place in chloroform but a very feeble reaction is noticed in presence of moisture, though no sufficient quantity for analysis could be separated. In benzene, even when heated with constant shaking for 6-8 hours, there is no reaction and like platinum chloride, iridium chloride reacts with ethyl sulphide, methyl sulphide, diethyl disulphide or dimethyl disulphide in absence of alcohol or acetone, etc., though after prolonged contact, with evolution of hydrochloric acid. Moreover, even in presence of dilute aqua regia, in alcohol the same product $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ is obtained. All these point to the fact that iridium chloride in solution is first reduced and then reacts with the sulphide present; the presence of a small amount of chlorine in solution cannot prevent the reduction. That iridium trichloride is formed, has been further proved by the isolation of its soluble variety when dimethyl disulphide was allowed to act on iridium tetrachloride in alcohol in presence of a small amount of aqua regia (this will form the subject of a subsequent communication).

It has already been shown (*loc. cit.*) that by the action of ethyl sulphide on iridium tetrachloride in presence of hot alcohol under reflux, a compound of the formula $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (m. p. 131°) was obtained. It was noticed there that a very minute quantity of an insoluble powder also separated. The yield of this substance has

been found to increase if the above reaction is conducted in cold. It possesses the same chemical composition as the other compound but differs from it in colour, solubility and melting point. The present compound, when crystallised from hot acetone, is obtained in brownish-red shining needles but when powdered or precipitated from its solution, it is of light pink colour and is stable even when heated up to 200°. It is insoluble in benzene, sparingly so in alcohol and acetone but extremely soluble in chloroform, whereas the previous orange coloured substance is extremely soluble in benzene and also soluble in most of the organic solvents including ether.

Theoretically two isomers of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3 \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ are possible, *e.g.*,

Cis (I)

Trans (II)

By his exhaustive works on isomerism in iridium complexes, Delepine has established that the *cis*- compound is always orange and the *trans*, red. By analogy, the constitution of the red compound should be (II) and that of the orange one, (I). By the action of pyridine on (I), two compounds of the formulæ $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot \text{Py} \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Py} \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ have been obtained. Both the compounds are orange-yellow, soluble in acetone and extremely so in chloroform and pyridine and have sharp melting points. Their acetone solutions do not give any precipitate with silver nitrate in the same solvent. The remaining Et_2S could not be replaced by pyridine even when the reactants were heated in a sealed tube at 140-50° for 10 hours. These may be represented as:

(III)

(IV)

The melting point rises gradually as each of the Et_2S group is replaced by pyridine, *e.g.*, (I) melts at 131°, (III) at 171-72°, and

(IV) at 260° . Similar cases of partial replacement of ethyl sulphide by pyridine, ethylamine and piperidine, etc., is not uncommon in platinum compounds (cf. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 361).

By the action of benzyl sulphide on iridium tetrachloride $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ has been obtained. As the chlorine does not ionise in solution, it can be represented like (I). Along with this, a red compound is also formed but it has not yet been isolated in the pure state.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (red variety, m.p. 171°).—Iridium tetrachloride (8 g.) and ethyl sulphide (8 c.c.) in alcohol (30 c.c.) were mixed together and kept corked for 12 days with occasional stirring and then the solution filtered to separate a very small quantity of greyish black mass, probably reduced iridium, which gradually formed during the reaction. The deep red filtrate was then concentrated in vacuum over calcium chloride for 2 days when a crystalline substance separated out. The crystals were collected, washed free from the adhering liquid with benzene and finally with cold acetone, m.p. $159\text{--}60^{\circ}$. This on further crystallisation (4 times) from a mixture of chloroform and acetone melts at 171° . It is a brownish-red shining substance but when obtained as a precipitate from chloroform or acetone solution or powdered, it is flesh coloured. The filtrate was then treated as recorded in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*). (Found: Cl, 17.92; S, 16.9, 17.3; Ir, 33.6. $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ requires Cl, 18.68; S, 17.03; Ir, 33.86 per cent).

Preparation of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot \text{Py} \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$.—To a solution of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (2 g.) in benzene (20 c. c.), pyridine (3 c.c.) was added and the mixture heated under reflux on a water-bath for 10—12 hours and then for another 6—7 hours without a condenser. Shining yellow crystals separated out on cooling. These were collected, washed with a small quantity of cold benzene and digested with acetone (hot) when almost the whole of the substance went into solution leaving a very small quantity, also insoluble in hot chloroform and pyridine, melting at 222° (decomp.). From the acetone solution, glistening yellow crystalline substance was obtained and this when twice crystallised from the same solvent melted at $171\text{--}72^{\circ}$. The main filtrate on dilution with a mixture of acetone and water yielded the above substance, m. p. $171\text{--}72^{\circ}$, when crystallised

several times from acetone. It is soluble in benzene and acetone sparingly so in alcohol but freely in chloroform. In acetone solution it does not give any precipitate with silver nitrate in the same solvent. (Found: Cl, 19.2; S, 11.0; Ir, 34.25. $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot \text{Py} \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ requires Cl, 19.05; S, 11.4; Ir, 34.5 per cent).

Preparation of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot 2\text{Py}$.— $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (1.5 g.) in pyridine (5 c. c.) was heated in a sealed tube for 4 hours at 120-25° and then for another 4 hours at 145-50°. Before heating, the $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ was in solution but after heating and cooling the tube a fair amount of a yellow crystalline substance was found to separate (B). The pyridine solution was decanted off and this on dilution yielded a dirty yellow precipitate. It was collected and crystallised from acetone, m. p. 236-40°(A); but on fractionally crystallising it thrice from acetone, the melting point rose up to 258° and on analysis found to be identical with (B). The solid crystalline substance was washed with acetone (cold) and ether to remove the last trace of pyridine and then crystallised from hot chloroform, m. p. 258°. When again dissolved in acetone, it was found that a very small portion containing a white and a red substance did not pass into solution but the quantity being too small it was not further dealt with. The melting point was finally found to be 260° (B). (Found: N, 4.8; S, 5.75; Cl, 19.7; Ir, 35.37. $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot 2\text{Py}$ requires N, 5.1; S, 5.85; Cl, 19.4; Ir, 35.28 per cent).

Preparation of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$.—In a stoppered conical flask, iridium chloride (6 g.), benzyl sulphide (13.6 g.) and alcohol (75 c. c.) were taken together and kept closed. The chloride took about 4 hours to go into solution and the sulphide about 20 hours. After 24 hours a yellow precipitate began to separate slowly and this, once begun, went on for a week when a tarry substance was first noticed to separate along with the yellow substance. The solid substance was then collected and dissolved in benzene from which on spontaneous evaporation, it was obtained in pale yellow colour, m. p. 201°. It is highly soluble in benzene and chloroform. (Found: Cl, 11.2; S, 9.76; Ir, 20.4. $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ requires Cl, 11.31; S, 10.19; Ir, 20.49 per cent).

Action of ethyl sulphide on ammonium chloriridate.—Ethyl sulphide (2 c. c.) was added to ammonium chloriridate (about 2 g.) in water (50 c. c.) and alcohol (6 c. c.) and it was heated under reflux on a water-bath for 8—10 hours, when gradually a yellow substance separated out, mixed with a little of a red variety. The solid substance

was separated and digested under reflux with acetone. This extract on concentration yielded $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3 \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ mixed with a small quantity of a dirty white substance having no m. p. The insoluble residue (m. p. 210°) was then crystallised twice from chloroform in which it was found to be slightly soluble, m. p. 222° (decomp.). In our previous paper (*loc. cit.*) the m. p. of this compound was stated to be 207° at which it decomposes. But now on recrystallising the same sample 4 times from chloroform, it has been found to melt with decomposition at 222° . (Found: S, 13.53; Ir, 41.74. $\text{Ir}_2 \text{Cl}_5 \cdot 4 \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ requires S, 13.86; Ir, 41.82 per cent).

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

Received June 2, 1933.

